

In-situ Monitoring of Delamination in CFRP Laminates during Drilling

Keiji Ogi

Mitsuyoshi Tsutsumi

Koichi Mizukami

Ehime University

Purpose and background

CFRP (Carbon Fiber Reinforced Plastic) Laminate

Drilling: necessary for mechanical fastening

Issue in drilling

Constraining **delamination** that leads to strength degradation due to machining

Delamination : detected by non-destructive inspection (NDI) after drilling

Difficult to know (1) strain during drilling, (2) timing of delamination, (3) thrust force for delamination (**critical thrust force F_d**)

Purpose : measure F_d from the parameters measured during drilling

Flow chart of experiment

Push-in test

Obtain the calibration curve of the thrust force against the strain of the back-up board (thrust strain)

Drilling test

Measure the (1) thrust strain, (2) internal strain (using an FBG sensor), and (3) **electrical impedance** (magnitude and phase angle) to determine the **timing of POD and the corresponding thrust strain**

Estimation the **critical thrust force** from the calibration curve obtained from the push-in tests and the thrust strain from drilling tests

In-situ strain and damage monitoring

electrical impedance

(magnitude and phase angle)

Measured by connecting an LCR meter (frequency 1 kHz) to the electrode (conductive paste) around the drilled hole

Electrical impedance in the thickness direction has a resistance component R and a capacitance component C

→ High possibility of detecting the timing of delamination during drilling

Internal strain

(1) FBG sensor embedded in the specimen

(2) Temperature using TC bonded to CFRP front and back surfaces

Conversion formula

$$\varepsilon (\mu\varepsilon) = \frac{1 \times 10^6}{F_G} \frac{\Delta\lambda}{\lambda_0} - \left(\frac{C_1}{F_G} - C_2 \right) \Delta T$$

$\Delta\lambda$: Bragg wave length shift

F_G [-]	C_1 [$\mu\text{m}/\text{m}/\text{K}$]	C_2 [$\mu\text{m}/\text{m}/\text{K}$]	λ_0 [nm]
0.838	6.156	0.7	1550

Specimens

Prepreg	Length	Width	Thickness	Stacking sequence
CF/Epoxy (T700S/2592 Vf=0.6)	80 mm	80 mm	2 mm	16-ply QI laminate [45° ₂ /90° ₂ /-45° ₂ /0° ₂] _s

Cure condition using an autoclave
 Temp: 130°C for 2 hr under vacuum
 Pressure: 0.3 MPa

Resistivity

Fiber: $5.9 \times 10^{-5} \Omega \cdot m$

Transverse: $7.9 \times 10^{-2} \Omega \cdot m$

Thickness: $1.0 \times 10^{-1} \Omega \cdot m$

FBG sensor
 Middle of the two
 90°-layers

Experimental setup for in-situ monitoring

Drilling test

Detail of CFRP work

1. Investigate the thrust strain and impedance vs. time diagrams
2. Determine the timing of POD t_d
3. Estimate the thrust strain at the timing of POD ε_d

Push-in test

1. For several drilling displacements z , a universal testing machine was used to measure the relationship between thrust strain ϵ and thrust force F by pressing the same drill bit as the drilling test into a pre-drilled hole
2. Create a calibration curve averaging the results for several drilling displacements z

Estimate the critical thrust force from the results of drilling and push-in tests

Critical thrust force F_d

Calibration curve

Results of push-in test

Thrust load-strain diagram is independent of drilling displacement

Calibration curve (red): average of results for each drilling displacement

Cross-section after drilling (1) large POD

Impedance and strains (1) large POD

Rotation speed	Feed rate
540 [rpm]	0.6 [mm/s]

2.2 mm

- Maximum thrust strain
 - $|\Delta Z|/|Z|$ is plateau
 - $\Delta\theta$ is plateau
- Initiation of POD

2.5mm

- Further reduce in thrust strain
 - Sudden increase in $|\Delta Z|/|Z|$
 - Sudden decrease in $\Delta\theta$
- Propagation of POD

Estimation of critical thrust force

Drilling displacement for POD: $y = 2.2$ mm

Thrust strain for POD: $\epsilon_d = 860$ $\mu\epsilon$

Critical thrust force for POD: $F_d = 183$ N

Cross-section after drilling (2) small POD

z=2.1 mm

z=2.4 mm

POD

z=2.7 mm

Small amount of POD development

POD

1mm

Impedance and strains (2) small POD

Rotation speed	Feed rate
2610 [rpm]	0.1 [mm/s]

**Small changes in the signals
→ Unclear signs (small changes)
showing delamination onset**

Improvement of electrodes

Circular electrodes are used to capture **POD smaller than the diameter of the drilled hole**

Impedance and strains (2) small POD

- A:** Plateau starting point, **B:** Onset of POD
- C:** End of POD extension, **D:** penetration of drill tip
- E:** full penetration of drill lead part ($\phi 6$)

Thrust strain for POD:

Critical thrust force : $F_d = 42 \text{ N}$

Conclusions

- 1. The thrust force for POD onset in CFRP drilling was estimated from impedance changes.**
- 2. Onset and propagation of large POD can be clearly detected by the electrical impedance method, whereas for small POD, the impedance change is relatively less clear.**
- 3. POD detection sensitivity is improved by changing from ring-shaped electrodes to circular electrodes.**
- 4. Since POD does not always occur at the maximum thrust force, POD onset cannot be detected from the thrust force alone.**